

Mortality in Patients Diagnosed with Dengue Treated at a Second-Level Hospital in Mexico

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ABSTRACT

Background: Dengue is one of the most important vector-borne diseases worldwide and continues to be a major public health problem in tropical regions¹. Although most cases are self-limited, severe dengue can lead to complications and death². Identifying clinical factors associated with mortality is essential to improve early detection and timely management³.

Objective: To determine mortality and associated clinical factors in patients diagnosed with dengue treated at a second-level hospital in Mexico.

Methods: A retrospective observational study was conducted using medical records of patients diagnosed with dengue between January and December 2023 at a second-level hospital in Veracruz, Mexico. Sociodemographic and clinical variables were analyzed. Descriptive statistics and bivariate analysis using the chi-square test were performed to identify variables associated with mortality. Statistical analysis was carried out using SPSS version 25.

Results: A total of 850 patients were included in the study after excluding incomplete records. The mean age was 42 ± 9.6 years, with 59.1% women (n=502) and 40.9% men (n=348). Most patients were managed on an outpatient basis, while a smaller proportion required hospitalization.

Nineteen deaths associated with dengue were identified. Bivariate analysis showed statistically significant associations between mortality and clinical severity variables such as shock, respiratory distress, classification as severe dengue, thrombocytopenia, and hypoalbuminemia.

Conclusions: Mortality associated with dengue in this hospital setting was mainly related to severe clinical manifestations and laboratory abnormalities linked to plasma leakage and hemodynamic instability. Early identification of these factors may improve clinical outcomes and reduce dengue-related mortality.

KEYWORDS: Dengue, mortality, severe dengue, epidemiology, thrombocytopenia, Mexico.

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INTRODUCTION

According to the World Health Organization, disease is defined as an alteration of the organism's physiological state manifested by characteristic signs and symptoms. Dengue is a viral disease transmitted by mosquitoes of the *Aedes* genus, caused by the dengue virus belonging to the *Flaviviridae* family¹². It is characterized by fever, severe headache, retro-orbital pain, myalgia, arthralgia, and erythema, and may present from mild forms to debilitating conditions³.

In recent decades, global incidence has increased

considerably, with an estimated 390 million infections annually, of which approximately 96 million present clinical manifestations. In 2022, more than 2.8 million cases were reported, confirming its importance as a global public health problem⁴⁵. Currently, the disease is distributed in more than 120 countries and represents a risk for approximately 3.9 billion people⁶⁷.

The World Health Organization classifies the disease according to severity into non-severe dengue, dengue with warning signs, and severe dengue⁸. Although most cases have

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a favorable course, complicated forms can have a fatality rate close to 5%, which may increase up to 25% without timely treatment⁸⁹. The virus has a positive single-stranded RNA genome with five identified serotypes (DENV-1 to DENV-5), where infection confers long-lasting specific immunity but only temporary protection against other serotypes^{10,12}.

Clinically, dengue presents three phases: febrile, critical, and recovery. During the febrile phase, fever, headache, myalgia, and retro-orbital pain predominate; this may be followed by a critical phase with plasma leakage, hemorrhage, or shock; finally, fluid reabsorption occurs during the convalescent phase¹¹. The pathophysiology of severe dengue is related to endothelial dysfunction and increased vascular permeability, leading to plasma extravasation between the third and sixth day of illness¹³.

Various studies describe that infection may be asymptomatic in up to 75–85% of cases or present with mild or severe disease¹⁴. In severe cases, hemorrhagic manifestations, hemoconcentration, serous effusions, and hypovolemic shock have been identified as the main complications¹⁵. Additionally, secondary infection with a different serotype increases the risk of severe dengue due to the antibody-dependent enhancement phenomenon¹⁶.

Clinical criteria for severe dengue include severe plasma leakage with shock or respiratory distress, significant hemorrhage, and organ damage such as severe hepatitis, encephalitis, or myocarditis¹⁷. Epidemiological studies have identified various clinical markers associated with diagnosis or disease progression, such as rash, persistent vomiting, and capillary fragility¹⁸.

Other studies report that the most frequent symptoms are fever, headache, and retro-orbital pain, accompanied by thrombocytopenia in most patients¹⁹. Factors such as age under 15 years, history of dengue, and repeated consultations for the same clinical condition have been associated with a higher risk of developing severe dengue²⁰.

Environmental and behavioral factors, such as lack of mosquito nets or lack of knowledge of preventive measures, have also been identified as increasing infection risk²¹.

Recent research has identified clinical variables associated with severe progression, such as diabetes mellitus, abdominal pain, cough, lethargy, and hematological alterations²². In pediatric populations, the presence of pleural effusion and cardiovascular alterations is associated with a higher likelihood of admission to intensive care units²³. Among the most frequent complications are spontaneous bleeding,

thrombocytopenia, and coagulation disorders²⁴.

Likewise, some studies have identified predictive factors of mortality in severe dengue, such as hemodynamic alterations, metabolic acidosis, hyperglycemia, and pericardial effusion^{25,35}. Other reports describe that the most frequent warning signs in fatal cases include abdominal pain, serous effusions, altered consciousness, and comorbidities such as hypertension²⁶.

From a pathophysiological perspective, several inflammatory biomarkers such as TNF- α , ST2, and TRAIL have been associated with a higher probability of progression to severe dengue during the early stages of infection²⁷. It has also been observed that dengue epidemics may increase due to climatic factors, as occurred during the Coastal El Niño phenomenon in Peru, where a significant increase in cases and mortality was reported²⁸.

Recent epidemiological studies have indicated that dengue mortality is associated with comorbidities, hemorrhage, hepatitis, hypoproteinemia, and hypoalbuminemia, highlighting the influence of both infection severity and patients' preexisting conditions^{29,30}. In Mexico, a case analysis reported higher mortality among individuals aged 11 to 40 years and a predominance of deaths during peak transmission months, between August and November^{31,32}.

In cases of dengue shock, the most frequent clinical manifestations include tachycardia, pallor, altered consciousness, circulatory failure, and a weak, rapid pulse, while less commonly observed findings include cold skin, severe hypotension, and decreased pulse pressure³³. In many patients who progress to death, signs of shock, organ failure, and metabolic acidosis are identified during the clinical course³⁴.

Regarding predictive values for mortality, a case study conducted in 2018 found that key parameters included mean arterial pressure and urine output at time point 3, blood glucose levels at time points 2 and 3, metabolic acidosis with a base deficit (BD) ≥ -8 mmol/L at time points 1 and 2, and pericardial effusion in severe dengue³⁵.

RESULTS

Population Characteristics

A total of 896 patients were recorded during the study period from January 2023 to December 2023, of which 46 medical records did not meet the eligibility criteria for inclusion. Therefore, the final sample for analysis consisted of 850 patients.

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Figure 1. Patients included in the study
Source: Study database

The study population consisted of a total of 502 female patients and 348 male patients.

Table 1. Percentage distribution by sex.

Sex	Frequency	%
F	502	59
M	348	41

Source: Study database

Figure 2. Age distribution
Source: Study database

Regarding symptomatology, the most prevalent symptoms in the sample were identified and distributed as follows.

Table 2. Symptoms identified

Symptoms	Frequency	%
Fever	850	100
Headache	848	99
Rash	692	81
Arthralgia	838	98
Retro-orbital pain	792	93
Thrombocytopenia	582	68
Gingival bleeding	126	14
Bleeding at another site	8	.01
Vomiting	375	44

Source: Study database

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In terms of area of residence, patients were distributed as follows.

Table 3. Municipality of residence of the patients

City	Cases
U.h. potrerrillo i	14
Tlilapan	1
Sumidero	15
Rio blanco	102
Puerta grande	17
Potrerrillo	19
Palmira	38
Orizaba	296
Nogales	79
Mariano Escobedo	5
Jalapilla	28
Ixtaczoquitlan	48
Ixhuatlancillo	10
Huiloapan de Cuautemoc	5
Guayabal	16
Fraccionamiento valle dorado	4
Dos ríos (Tocuila)	12
Ciudad mendoza	78
Cordoba	48
Buenvista	15

Source: Study database

With respect to reported cases by epidemiological week, the highest number of cases was observed as follows.

Figure 3. Distribution of cases by week

Source: Study database

The most frequently identified serotypes were the following.

Figure 4. Identified serotypes

Source: Study database

The final diagnosis of patients treated at the hospital was as follows.

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Figure 5. Classification of dengue diagnosis
Source: Study database

Clinical Management

Regarding hospitalization, patients were managed either on an outpatient basis or as inpatients, with the following results.

Figure 6. Type of care in patients
Source: Study database

MORTALITY

During the study period, 19 deaths associated with dengue were identified. Although dengue was not always the primary cause of death, it was considered a contributing factor.

DISCUSSION

Dengue is a viral disease caused by dengue viruses (DENV), members of the *Flaviviridae* family belonging to the *Flavivirus* genus. It is of great importance due to its global impact and is defined by the World Health Organization as a disease being an “alteration or deviation of the physiological state in one or more parts of the body, generally due to known causes, manifested by characteristic signs and symptoms, and whose course is more or less predictable.”

The central focus of this thesis was dengue-related mortality. Dalrymple (2012) analyzed the characteristics of severe cases and their main complications, observing that these present hemorrhagic manifestations, increased hematocrit due to plasma loss secondary to increased vascular permeability, as well as serous effusions and hypovolemic shock.

In our study, most complications occurred in patients with the DEN-2 serotype, presenting manifestations consistent with plasma leakage. Hemorrhagic manifestations were also observed.

In 2010, Suárez L and collaborators conducted a case-control study in which, through logistic regression, they identified the following risk factors for severe dengue: age under 15 years,

previous dengue infection, and returning to a healthcare facility for the same clinical condition. Additionally, the most frequent warning signs were abdominal pain, mucosal bleeding, and persistent vomiting, which appeared on average between the third and fifth day from symptom onset.

In the present research, age was indeed identified as a risk factor, particularly at extreme ages. In pediatric patients, there was a higher risk of decompensation. Regarding sex, there were more cases in women (59%) compared to men (41%); however, mortality was higher in men, accounting for 63% of deaths.

Arthralgia and fever were present in almost the entire sample, being the most frequent symptoms. In terms of complications, shock was the most notable finding.

Rojas M analyzed factors associated with progression to severe dengue in 146 patients from a tertiary-level hospital in Paraguay (2019–2020). Associations were found with diabetes mellitus, intermittent abdominal pain, and cough, while female sex and leukopenia acted as protective factors. Complications were related to male sex and comorbidities, and mortality was associated with shock, dyspnea, diagnosis of severe dengue, hypoalbuminemia, and thrombocytopenia. Similarly, Pinheiro FP (2018), in a case study in Mexico, reported higher mortality among individuals aged 11 to 40 years; 58% of cases were female, and most deaths occurred between August and November. Additionally, a significant proportion of patients had only primary education^{31,32}.

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In the analyzed sample, there was likewise a predominance of males, but with higher lethality in females; dengue lethality was 2.2% of the total. Regarding occupation, it was higher among the working-age population, but with a significant proportion of students.

Guzmán MG (2020) described the most frequent manifestations in patients with dengue shock. The predominant signs were tachycardia, pallor, altered consciousness, circulatory failure, and a weak, rapid pulse; less frequently cold skin, systolic blood pressure below 60 mmHg, and narrowing of pulse pressure to less than 20 mmHg³³.

This behaved very similarly in our analyzed sample, with manifestations of dyspnea, tachycardia, hepatic failure, and circulatory failure.

CONCLUSION

Dengue is a viral disease transmitted to humans through the bite of infected mosquitoes. Currently, nearly half of the world's population is at risk of infection, with an estimated 100 to 400 million infections occurring each year. In more than 500,000 severe cases, it causes approximately 24,000 deaths annually.

Understanding the pathophysiology of the disease is essential, as well as dengue lethality; in our study, lethality was measured at 2.2% of the total sample.

The factors most associated with severity and mortality were age under 10 years and over 60 years, as well as the presence of comorbidities. The most severe complication was plasma leakage, leading to hypovolemic shock and, in some cases, septic shock.

Therefore, knowledge of the operational definitions for dengue diagnosis is fundamental to ensure timely treatment and prevent complications.

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